

“Novel leads and drugs for vector borne diseases: Targets and off targets (toxicity and ecotoxicity) and mechanism of action”
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Development of NMT-A004-loaded biodegradable nanocarriers

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Neglected infectious diseases (NIDs) caused by protozoan parasites belonging to the genera *Leishmania* and *Trypanosoma* have high mortality and morbidity rates, affecting impoverished populations in the developing world [1]. Current therapies can have issues such as toxicity or teratogenicity, while clinical resistance is on the rise. Thus, the discovery of new, safe and inexpensive drugs for NIDs is an ongoing challenge.

Calogeropoulou’s group has pioneered the development of improved ether phospholipid derivatives, possessing enhanced antileishmanial and/or antitrypanosomal activity and reduced toxicity. In particular, an alkyl phosphocholine-dinitroaniline hybrid **NMT-A004** [2] exhibited a broad spectrum antiparasitic activity against *Leishmania*, *T. brucei* and *T. cruzi* Y strain epimastigotes, intracellular amastigotes and trypomastigotes. However, its SNAP-PK evaluation showed reduced oral bioavailability. To address this issue we developed and characterized biodegradable nanostructured vectors that increase its half-life.

The *in silico* studies showed the lipophilic character of the compound giving insights about the formulation design challenges. Three types of unloaded and **NMT-A004**-loaded nanocarriers were produced:

A) Lipid cubosomes, **B) Polymeric cubosomes** and **C) Nanostructured Lipid Carriers (NLCs)** (Figure 1). The encapsulation of **NMT-A004** was performed in three concentrations (10, 100 and 1000 µM) by incubation

or direct mixing methods and the corresponding encapsulation efficiency (EE%) and drug loading (DL%) were determined by the developed validated quantification method.

Thus, **15** successful formulations were produced and characterized in terms of mean particle size, polydispersity index (PDI), surface charge (zeta potential) and colloidal-stability (4 weeks). The negative charge polymeric cubosomes seem more stable than the positive charge lipidic ones despite their bigger sizes. Moreover, the negative charge NLCs were also stable with very small sizes but higher PDI. Finally, all the formulations present EE% close to 100% and in terms of drug loading, lipid cubosomes had the higher drug content (>15 % for 1000 µM of **NMT-A004**). The *in vitro* release studies are *in progress*.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the biodegradable nanocarrier systems

References

- [1] Global report on neglected tropical diseases 2023, WHO report (2023), <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240067295>
- [2] M. Roussaki, G. E. Magoulas, T. Fotopoulou, N. Santarem, E. Barrias, I. Pöhner, S. Luelmo, P. Afroudakis, K. Georgikopoulou, P. T. Nevado, J. Eick, E. Bifeld, M. J. Corral, M. D. Jim´enez-Ant´on, B. Ellinger, M. Kuzikov, I. Fragiadaki, E. Scoulica, S. Gul, J. Clos, K. C. Prousis, J. J. Torrado, José M. Alunda, R. C. Wade, W. de Souza, A. Cordeiro da Silva, T. Calogeropoulou (2023), Design, synthesis and biological evaluation of antiparasitic dinitroaniline-ether phospholipid hybrids. *Bioorganic Chemistry*, 138, 106615

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